

TEACHING METHODOLOGY BY COMPARING ENGLISH GRAMMAR TO NATIVE LANGUAGE GRAMMAR

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Abstract. *This article tried to provide information on teaching English grammar by comparing it to native language grammar.*

Keywords: *group of English languages, morphological stage, grammar system, word order.*

МЕТОДИКА ОБУЧЕНИЯ ПУТЕМ СРАВНЕНИЯ ГРАММАТИКИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА С ГРАММАТИКОЙ РОДНОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В этой статье мы попытались предоставить информацию о преподавании английской грамматики, сравнивая ее с грамматикой родного языка.*

Ключевые слова: *группа английских языков, морфологический этап, грамматическая система, порядок слов.*

As you know, English and Uzbek languages belong to separate language groups. While English belongs to the group of Germanic languages of the Indo-European language family, Uzbek belongs to the group of Turkic languages. But if the grammar systems of these languages are compared with each other, then at their stages we will witness similar phenomena on the one hand and different on the other. In the morphological stage, analogies between the grammar system of both languages are found in nouns in the suffixes of numbers, conjugation, and in verbs in the suffixes of the categories tense, ratio, declination, person and number.

The same should be noted separately that grammatical means in these categories are very few in English. At the same time, we also find significant differences in the expression and meaning of these categories. Although the expression of the number category in English and Uzbek, for example, is made by adding suffixes, significant different places in this category cause many difficulties to arise.

Example:

Five books-five books,

Ten students-ten students

The word is considered a phenomenon typical of the English language by making a plural form by changing the vowel in its core.

Despite the fact that the noun word category in English and Uzbek has a conjugate category, the number of conjugate suffixes is not the same in both comparable languages. There are 6 cache suffixes in Uzbek, and in English there are only two of them.

In the syntactic part of both languages, on the one hand, we encounter similar signs, and on the other hand, we come across phenomena that are characteristic only of one language itself. For example: the syllabic, interrogative and non-divisive forms of sentences are considered a syntactic phenomenon characteristic of both languages. But if we analyze the word order in darak sentences, we will witness that the word order in the sentence in English is much more

strict than in the Uzbek language. In Uzbek, the word order in a sentence is considered more free than in English.

Taking into account the language experience of students when teaching grammar. From methodological literature, we know that teaching a foreign language at school is carried out in bilingual conditions. Streamers will have language experience in their native language and Russian language until they learn a foreign language.

They acquire many grammatical terms, phenomena, rules and qualifications regarding their native language and the Russian language. This experience in them should be taken into account by the teacher who is teaching English in this class, in the group, and teach them to use students in the required places. When teaching students many phenomena of the morphology of the English language, it is possible to carry out a positive transfer from the experience of the native language and the language of the Russian language acquired by them. For example, prepositions in English are a difficult material for students to master, the reason for which is that, firstly, there are no prepositions in Uzbek. Second prepositions as a word series represent preachy (abstract) concepts, so students have many difficulties in mastering them.

It is V preposition in sentences. When explaining prepositions, it is advisable to take into account the experience of the Russian language. The use of linguistic experience in the Russian language is not without benefit, even when introducing or explaining structures that have the form of a future tense in the English language. In teaching some grammatical phenomena in the first and second stages of teaching English, language experience related to English grammar is also used, which is mastered by student students. For example, if the student students studied the functions of the infinitive in the sentence, then the experience acquired by relation to the infinitive is taken into account at the time of study by them.

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